

ISic4352

I.Sicily inscription 4352

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

2016.05.12

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)**Place of origin (modern)**

Sicily

Provenance

exact provenance unknown

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo di Archeologia
dell'Universita di Catania, inventory 05/258

Physical Description**Dimensions**

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout**Execution**

Engraved

Letter Forms**Letter heights:**

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text**Apparatus****Translation****Commentary****Digital identifiers:****Bibliography**

Biondi, G., Buscemi Felici, G. 2014. Iscrizioni. In Biondi, G., Buscemi Felici, G., Tortorici, E.(eds.), *Il museo archeologico dell'Università di Catania. Collezione Libertini*. Acireale. pp. 170-173. At 171 no.241 fig.42

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